

The Voynich Manuscript: A New Paleographic and Linguistic Reassessment of Folio 116v

Abstract

This study examines the brief annotation on fol. 116v, which – unlike the main body of the manuscript – is written unencoded in Gothic cursive with the exception of two encrypted words. It analyzes the content from linguistic, paleographic, and pharmaceutical perspectives and demonstrates that the text exhibits a coherent and plausible meaning.

Evidence indicates that the note is written in Early New High German with Bavarian features and Latin pharmaceutical terminology. Several technical terms appear in highly abbreviated form, and this study offers the first systematic resolution of these abbreviations. Earlier attempts at interpretation have described the text as chaotic or merely as meaningless gibberish, and it has likewise been regarded as a prayer or a magical formula yet it can be shown that it is in fact a pharmaceutical recipe with meaningful context and logical syntax. This indicates that all previous readings were incorrect and misinterpreted the content. It is demonstrated that the content represents the note of an ointment recipe. The analysis further demonstrates that the language can be identified as Central Bavarian; however, the author was not a native speaker of German. The orthography has turned out to be a strongly phonetic rendering, closely reflecting the dialectal pronunciation. This explains why earlier interpretations failed to produce any meaningful context or content. In addition, several letter forms of the Gothic cursive script were not read correctly, and this study provides corrected readings that resolve long-standing misunderstandings of the text.

The writing style aligns with the manuscript's radiocarbon dating (1404–1438). Overall, the study opens new perspectives for research on the Voynich Manuscript, particularly regarding the linguistic region in which this note originated and the author's most likely region of origin.

Analysis of Folio f 116v

The Voynich Manuscript is a mysterious 15th century codex written in an unknown cipher and unidentified language. The book is considered one of the most enigmatic codices of the 15th century. It was discovered in 1912 by Wilfried Voynich in a former Jesuit college in northern Italy. The author is unknown and numerous hypotheses have been proposed concerning the content and the language underlying its glyphs. The parchment analysis indicated a period between 1404 and 1438. Despite centuries of research, neither its script nor its language has been deciphered, and its content remains unknown to this day.

The brief note on folio 116v has repeatedly attracted particular attention. Although it is not encrypted - except for two words written in cipher - its difficult-to-read handwriting, combined with numerous abbreviations, has so far prevented any secure reading. As a result, none of the proposed interpretations has produced a convincing, internally consistent meaning, and the note has sometimes been dismissed as meaningless scribble.

A correct reading depends crucially on recognizing that this note was written in Central Bavarian dialect, and that understanding this dialect is essential for an accurate interpretation. The Latin

pharmaceutical terminology presents an additional difficulty, as such terms are integrated into the dialect text and often appear in heavily abbreviated form. Forms previously classified as “non-linguistic” (no real language, merely scribbles to test the pen, etc.) turn out to be regular dialectal word groups whose faulty word separation created the false impression of a text without structure. There is considerable evidence that the author was most likely not a native speaker of German. A person with only limited command of German as a second language does not automatically recognize word boundaries; they write what they perceive acoustically, and the dialect further obscures these boundaries. The text remained puzzling because the language was not recognized as Central Bavarian, the Gothic cursive script with its ambiguous letter forms was frequently misread, the spelling is strongly phonetic, and the handwriting is difficult to decipher.

The incorrect or entirely missing word spaces had gone unnoticed until now. What appears to be a single word is in fact a sequence of multiple words written without word separation. For example, the word that looks like *anchiton* must be read correctly as *an c hi ton* (*apply to toe*) and certainly not as *michiton*. Likewise, *valscn uzvey* actually consists of five words and therefore must be read *vals c nu z vey* (*if toe now too painful*). Reading *valsen uBrey* is not correct.

Even for German-speaking scholars, the Bavarian dialectal features present in the text can be difficult to identify, especially when combined with the scribe’s inconsistent word separation. The Gothic letter *tz* was often mistakenly read as an uppercase B. The author’s spelling *c* for *Zeh* is an unusual orthographic variant, because in German the letter *c* sounds the same as the word *Zeh* (*toe*). Here, the author reduces a complex German word to a single letter. Since “*Zeh*” [tse] sounds like a hissing sound to him, he uses *c*. This is a classic case of “spelling by ear” by a non-German native speaker. Although there was no standardized spelling at the time, certain rules were followed. This scribe, however, hardly adhered to it. Therefore, it is highly probable that German was a second language for him.

Distinct characteristics allow a fairly precise classification as Central Bavarian dialect of which is assigned to the Upper German language group. This fact is evident through features such as the initial sound shift *b > p* in *poxleber*, *olas* for *alles*, *ceuc* for *Kalk*, and the diphthong shift *ei > a* in *gasmich* for *Geißenmilch*, terms that will be clarified subsequently. Such words resemble an actually heard linguistic variety rather than accidental spellings. The author appears unfamiliar with *f*, *pf*, and *w*, consistently substituting *v* for these graphemes.

The use of only the letter *s* to represent the sibilant *sch* at word endings is also striking.

These features point clearly to this linguistic variety. Central Bavarian is spoken not only in southern Germany but also in neighboring parts of Austria.

The surprising new perspective suggesting a non-German author was put forward by German-studies experts at the Universities of Innsbruck, Vienna, and Salzburg. His exact spoken usage remains unknown, yet his written language shows clear adaptation to the dialectal environment and he retained certain writing habits from his earlier background. For his writing pattern contains indications of a possible origin in a Romance-language region. However, a Slavic-speaking region cannot be ruled out either.

Nevertheless, he must have been literate and well-educated as evidenced by the pharmaceutical instructions and the use of Latin technical abbreviations. This unusual combination of non-native German, Bavarian dialect and specialized Latin terminology helps explain why the text long appeared inscrutable, and why earlier attempts at interpretation failed to produce a logical and coherent reading.

A paleographic analysis of some letter forms - particularly the clear distinction between *r* and *v*, *b* and *z*, as well as the reconstruction of missing word boundaries - makes a coherent reading of the passage possible and leads to logical interpretation and demonstrates that there is a meaningful content.

The pharmaceutical plausibility of the recipe was confirmed through consultation with a representative of the Austrian Chamber of Pharmacists and with regional pharmacists. By examining both the ingredients and the manufacturing steps, they were able to determine and clarify the underlying meaning of tricky abbreviations such as *ma* for *macerate*, *six* for *salix* (*willow*), and especially *ma+ via* for *mana in vitra* (*"pour it into glass vessels"*). They also recognized that the ointment included an additive made in the form of a soft soap produced from potash and quicklime. The mixing of these ingredients is indicated in the recipe by the common pharmaceutical abbreviation *M* (*misce*). In the Middle Ages, soft soap was produced from potash and quicklime, ingredients mentioned in the recipe. Its addition to ointments served as an emulsifying and softening agent, improving both the consistency of the preparation and the absorption of the active ingredients.

Reconstructing the recipe yields a functional, internally consistent ointment for treating joint inflammation, of the kind well attested in late medieval sources; it was also prepared and reproduced successfully.

The crosses between the words indicate which ingredients need to be added and which production steps must be carried out. Because the Voynich Manuscript has a mystical reputation, they were often mistaken for Christian symbols; however, they are simply addition signs indicating the sequence of ingredients and the production steps to be carried out next. These signs must be read in their functional context and not viewed in isolation.

The text is written entirely in lowercase letters (with the exception of the single Gothic *M* for the pharmaceutical term *misce*) and shows no doubling of vowels or consonants, as seen in forms such as *nim* (Modern German *nimm*) or *vals* (Modern German *falls*).

The consistent lowercase spelling is a characteristic that the text still belongs to the Early New High German period until around 1450. Systematic capitalization developed much later, and it spread more slowly in the southern German and Austrian regions than, for example, in the Saxon area. Martin Luther increasingly used capital letters in his 1542 Bible edition, though still inconsistently. Only in the 17th and 18th centuries did capitalization become standardized. This provides an important indication of the text's date of origin. Such features correspond to the orthographic and phonetic conventions of the early 15th century and align with the manuscript's - respectively the parchment's - radiocarbon dating (1404 - 1438).

Taken together, they indicate an early stage of writing practice and strongly support the conclusion that the script and language of fol. 116v are contemporary with the main body of the manuscript, rather than a much later addition.

The note provides practical production instructions, presumably intended for an assistant in a monastic pharmacy. Directions such as "everything into a basin" and references to steeping or

cooling times indicate concrete procedural steps. The remark “if toe still too painful” and “then take goat’s milk” likewise corresponds to typical instructions found in late medieval medical recipes.

Earlier hypotheses claiming that the text represents a magical formula or a prayer can therefore be conclusively refuted.

In this study, the writer is referred to as male. Although a female authorship cannot be entirely excluded, it appears less probable. The Voynich-Manuscript is kept under the designation Beinecke MS 408 in the Beinecke Library of Rare Books in the USA.

Fol.116v

Beinecke MS 408

Central Bavarian with Latin:

poxleber vmen vot[n?] + ei

an c hi ton olas a bas(sin) + mvlto(ch) + tc + ca v cevc + povtas(ch) + M +
 s(al)ix + ma(cerat) vix + mo(llire) vix + V\X + atzia + ma(na) in vi(tr)a +
 ar(d)or ar(d)or (ar)t(ri)ticus vals c nv z vey so nim gasmich o...

Standard German:

Bocksleber um die Pfote + Ei

an Zeh hin tun alles (in)ein Bassin + Mulltasche + Talg + Branntkalk + Pottasche + M(misce)
 salix (Weide)+(ins)Mazerat Wachs + mollire Wachs(erweichen)+V\X + anziehen + gieße es in Gläser +
 ardor artriticus falls Zeh noch zu weh so nimm Geißenmilch o...

Standard English:

liver of a billy goat around the paw + egg

Apply to toe, everything into a basin + gauze bag + sebum + quicklime + potash + M(mix)
 salix (willow bark) + (into) macerate(put)wax + melt wax + V\X(minutes) + let get thickly + pour it into glasses +
 ardor artriticus if toe still too painful then take goatsmilk o...

Correct reading of graphem v: it represents four phonemes [f,u,v,w]. They are not distinguished and have to be interpreted according to the context. Character f does not exist in this text, this sound is always written with v.

Folio 116v	Standard German	English	Explanation
poxleber	Bocksleber	liver of a billy goat	b > p reflects Upper German spelling.
umen	um (d)en	around the	Articulated assimilation
vot[n?] forth letter is unlegible	Pfote? perhaps Pfo ⁿ (dialect)	Paw?	pf > v. A non-native author pronounces v [f] instead of <i>pf</i> . It is spelled v.
ei	Ei	egg	Not to be read "nutrifer" but votn + ei. Character <i>f</i> does not appear anywhere in this text. If the upper part of "f" is covered a plus sign appears.
an c hi ton	an Zeh hin tun	apply to toe	German c [tse] and Zeh [tse] for toe = same pronunciation; Appears without word separation <i>anchiton</i> .
olas a bas(in)	alles ein Basin	everything in a basin	
m[v]ltos = multosch	Mulltasche Mulltosch = Bavarian dialect and pronounced like [mooltʃsh]	gauze bag	A gauze bag was used to filter the willow bark. The symbol <i>ʒ</i> represents the sound [sch]. The spelling of trigraph <i>sch</i> was not yet standardized. > see povtas

Comparison of letter forms s of cursive gothic script:

The sample shows characteristic Gothic cursive letter forms. (A22 Brixen, 1400)

Round s resembles *d* in *lands*.

Round s looks similar to the number eight, *olaß a baß*.

Long gothic *s* as in *six, gasmich*, not character *f* since there is no horizontal stroke.

Upper German writing: *b > p*

poxleber : Standard German: *Bocksleber*

poxleber: Bocksleber

Bock (or *pock*) simply means *billy goat*. German words such as *Bocks*, *Lachs*, *Keks*, or *Text* all contain letter groups like *chs*, *cks*, *ks*, or *xt*, which in German are pronounced [ks]. The same applies to *poxleber*, where the character *x* likewise represents the [ks] sound. Spelling the sound [ks] with *x* is unusual in German and may suggest the spelling of a foreign scribe who simply wrote [ks] as *x*.

Why is it not *pockleber* here? The Fugen-*s* (linking *s*) of *Bocks* (*pox*) is a consonant inserted between the parts of a compound noun in German. Historically, the Fugen-*s* developed from genitive singular endings in Old and Middle High German. It has no semantic function and acts purely as a phonetic buffer.

In Upper German writing traditions, *b* and *p* are not consistently distinguished; this explains the spelling *poxleber* (*b > p*).

The liver of a male goat was commonly used as a remedy in medieval medicine. The goat's feet in the illustration appear to be marked, and the first sentence may refer to veterinary practice. In medieval iconography, the devil was also often depicted as a billy goat (Standard German *Bock*, upper German spelling *pock*).

However, no demonic symbolism is intended here; instead, it refers to an everyday ingredient in a recipe. Therefore, a mystical interpretation can no longer be upheld. It also has nothing to do with the disease *smallpox*. The important part is the second part of the word, namely *leber* (liver). In humoral medicine, the liver was considered warm and moist. It was applied as a poultice to the affected joint in cases of joint pain, and was also used in crushed form together with egg. The marginal drawing depicts a goat, presumably referring to the animal from which the liver was taken. Such illustrations were intended primarily for lay users.

vot[n?]: Pfofn (Engl.: paw)

The fourth letter is illegible, but by analogy it could be an *n*. In Bavarian dialect the vowel *e* in *Pfofen* is silent. It appears that the cluster *pf* does not exist in the scribe's native language and is difficult for him to pronounce. This may explain why the sound [f] is written with *v* instead.

Ei: Ei (Engl.: egg)

The final part of the word looks like *fer*. However, the small dot above the letter *i* which was often interpreted as part of the letter *r* is very likely just a stain on the parchment. The letter *f* does not occur anywhere in the text; this phoneme is consistently represented by *v*. The supposed *f* is in fact a plus sign. If the upper part is covered the shape clearly shows a plus sign. Egg was used as a binding agent, often in medicinal pastes. In combination with liver, it produces a spreadable, warming mass that could be applied to cloth or directly to the affected part of the body.

In medieval medical recipes, egg yolks and egg whites played an important pharmacological role and were used both externally and internally.

Reading „nutrifer“ is not correct.

poxleber

vmen

vot[n?] + ei

anchiton = an | c | hi | ton = (Standard German *an Zeh hin tun*)

The German letter *c* has the same pronunciation as the word *Zeh* (English *toe*). Using *c* to represent *Zeh* is an unusual spelling choice by the author. In the past, the word *anchiton* has already been read correctly once, but it was not recognized that it actually consists of four separate words written without spaces. The wrong reading ‘michiton’ is an interpretation that does not take into account the possibility of a regional dialect. The writer reduces the word *Zeh* to the single letter *c*, which is pronounced the same.

Multos = *Mulltosch*. This spelling represents the Bavarian pronunciation whereas *Mulltasche* is the Standard German form. The first element *mul(l)* (Standard German *Mull*) means *gauze*. The second element *tosch* corresponds to Standard German *Tasche* which means *bag* reflecting the typical Bavarian pronunciation dark *a* → *o*.

The scribe renders *sch* simply as *s* at the word ending. This is not a scribal error, since the spelling *sch* became established only gradually between 1350 and 1500. In medieval manuscripts the sibilant *sch* was frequently spelled *s*, *sc*, *sk*, *sh*, *hs*, *ss*.

Folio 116v	Standard German	English	Explanation
tc = talch/talc, Abbr. Historical spelling	Talg	tallow	An extract is made from willow bark in liquid hot tallow.
ca v (calx viva), Abbr.	Branntkalk	quicklime	Abbr. for calx viva (Latin)
cevc [keuk] v =[u] Vowel c = [k], spelling is influence by Latin	Kalk	lime	Unmistakably a Central Bavarian pronunciation with L-Vocalization. Consonant <i>ℓ</i> omitted. Kalk > [keuk]. Same sound as Eng. <i>Boy</i> , IPA: /kɔʏk/
povtaſ [poutasch]	Pottasche	potash	ſ = [sh] Trigraph <i>sch</i> developed gradually, replacing earlier spellings like <i>s</i> , <i>sk</i> , <i>sc</i> , <i>sh</i> , <i>hs</i> , and <i>ss</i> .
M Written with a Gothic capital letter	Mische!	Mix!	Misce! (lat.) M is a common pharmaceutical abbreviation
s(al)ix, (Latin)	Weide (Weidenrinde)	willow (willow bark)	Willow bark was used to produce an extract (oil macerate).

Glyph c: The glyph *c* shows inconsistent values, sometimes standing for the phonemes *t*, sometimes *k*, and sometimes *e*. In the encoded two words it represents also [i]. It can easily be confused and the meaning must therefore be determined from the context.

ca v = calx viva: This expression was firmly established as the standard term for unslaked or quicklime. The German word is: *Branntkalk*. The abbreviation *ca v* thus very likely represents an abbreviated form of *calx viva*. Tallow + *calx viva* + potash + *misce* → saponification occurs at this stage. *Calx viva* served as an excipient to produce lye; it was not an ingredient of the ointment itself. However, the resulting soft soap allowed the active components of the willow-bark extract to penetrate the skin more effectively.

ceuc: The writer adds the German dialect word *ceuc* (*lime*, Standard German *Kalk*) to ensure that the production was carried out correctly. Perhaps an assistant was involved in the practical work but was obviously less educated and did not understand the Latin technical terms. The omission of consonant *ℓ* is a typical feature of Central Bavarian dialect. The author writes this word

phonetically, providing indirect evidence of the regional sound realization in the Central Bavarian area. His use of the letter *c* for the phoneme [k] indicates a Latin influence and a period-typical older spelling convention (up to the 15th century). This orthographic convention was increasingly displaced during the 16th century. The content of the recipe forces this reading.

povtas: *v* = [u]. *Pottasche* in Standard German, English *potash*. Potash and quicklime are mixed (M) to form an alkaline lye. The lye reacts with the sebum and forms a soft ointment base. It served as an emulsifier and also had a therapeutic effect, as it enabled the constituents of the salicylate-containing willow bark to penetrate the skin more effectively.

V = [u]: The spelling *ou* is spelling by ear. One possible explanation for this spelling is that in parts of Styria - for example in Upper Styria and in adjacent dialect areas - the vowel *o* is diphthongized to *ou*. This is the border region between Germany and Austria, near the Alps — roughly the area around Salzburg and Berchtesgaden.

As previously noted with regard to *multos*, the scribe's use of *s* in place of *sch* at the end of a word may be due to the absence of this trigraph in the Latin alphabet or in his native language. The spelling *s* for *sch* is often found in medieval manuscripts. Between 1350 and 1500, the sibilant *sch* appears more frequently in writing; before *s,sk,sc,sh,hs* and *ss* are attested.

six = s(al)ix: The author uses an abbreviation for the Latin botanical term *salix* (*willow*). Willow bark was extracted in hot, liquid tallow for a period of time and then filtered with the *multos(ch)*, i.e. the gauze bag. It is unclear whether the finely chopped willow bark was placed directly into the melted fat or into the filter bag, which was then submerged in the fat together with its contents. Willow bark was well known for its pain-relieving properties.

Folio 116v	Standard German	English	Explanation
ma vix Wachs	Auszug (M azerat) Wachs	macerate wax	A macerated excerpt is prepared from chopped willow bark
mo vix mollire or mollifica	erweichen Wachs, auflösen	melt, soften	Wax is dissolved in the hot macerate by stirring
V\X Roman numerals from V to X (five to ten)	5-10 Minuten	5-10 minutes	Duration of softening/melting process.
atzia	anziehen lassen	let steep	Bavarian word ending <i>en</i> > <i>a</i>
ma ⁽ⁱⁿ⁾ via ma(na) in vi(tr)a	Gieße es in Gläser!	pour it into glasses!	A pharmaceutical term abbreviated. Imperativ.
ar_or - er ccg ar(d)or (ar)t(ri)t icus	Gelenkentzündung	joint inflammation	

ma: *macerate* or *macera* (Latin)

The most likely equivalents for *ma* are *macerate* (noun) or *macera* (imperative). An extract is produced by soaking willow bark in a liquid, such as heated tallow, for a certain period of time. Then wax is added. The missing plus sign between *ma* and *vix* does not change the meaning of the substance; it is most likely a case of carelessness in notation. The most plausible interpretation is therefore that it is a willow-bark macerate incorporated into a wax-based formulation.

vix: This is Bavarian dialect and a historical word for *Wachs* (English *wax*). Its etymology is documented by Jacob and Wilhelm Grimm in the *Wörterbuch der Deutschen Sprache* and derives from Old High German *wihsen*, meaning “to apply wax.” The letter groups *ch*, *ks*, *gs*, and *x* are all pronounced [ks] in German as in words like *Lachs*, *Fuchs*, *Keks*, *längs*, *Ochs* (*ox*) and were at times spelled with *x*. The word *Wichs* is still known today in Bavarian regions.

mo: It may be related to Latin *mollire* (English *to soften/to melt*) or *mollifica* as the second-person singular imperative of the Latin verb *mollificare*. The subsequent steps suggest a process of softening the wax. The wax is crushed and added to the warm macerate, then stirred until it fully softens. This duration of softening is 5-10 minutes as mentioned in the recipe. It is written in roman numerals.

atzia: *anziehen* in Standard German. As it is gently stirred 5-10 minutes and cools, the ointment begins to set and becomes noticeably thicker. The letters *z* and *tz* of the gothic cursive can easily be mixed up, but it would not change the meaning. It has to be read correctly *atzia* but *ahia* represents a misreading. Unlike the *tz*-ligature, the Gothic character *h* always has a downward loop, which is clearly visible in the word *gasmich*. The expression *anziehen* (in Bavarian dialect *atzia*) is a typical term used in the production of ointments.

ma(na) + (in) vi(tr)a

This shows the abbreviation of a pharmaceutical term *mana in vitra* that is still in use today as a apothecary term. In the recipe, it indicates that the preparation is complete and that the liquid ointment must now be poured into jars. The meaning of the plus sign between *ma* and *via* is ambiguous; very likely it represents the preposition *in*. *Vitra* is the plural of the Latin *vitrum* (“glass”) and signals that the recipe has reached its final step.

It is important not to confuse the glyphs **v** and **r**. These words were often interpreted as *ma ria*, but this is incorrect and makes no sense within this recipe. The scribe’s letter **r** is not open at the top like **v**, even though such a ductus does sometimes appear in some manuscripts. In this case, however, the author’s **r** has only a single vertical stem, as can be seen in *poxleber*. The misinterpretation of *mana in vitra* as *maria* led to the false assumption that the text was a prayer or blessing. The recipe ends logically with a standard Latin pharmaceutical expression and the instruction *mana in vitra* “pour into glass vessels”.

The production of the ointment is finished.

The variable phonemic interpretation of *v* and its contrast with *r*

r v = [u] v = [f]

poxleber vmen vot[n?]+ei

The pronunciation of [v] is shown in square brackets. The value of *v* is context-dependent: in some environments it behaves as a vowel, in others as a consonant.

The spelling of *votn* is an interference error by the scribe. It should read: *Pfotn*.

See separate explanation.

ca v cevc = **ca v = calx viva** cevc ceuc (quick lime)

ma + via ma(na) in vi(tr)a (pour into glass vessels)

The character v must be read as representing the sounds [v] and [u] - never r.

ca v = calx viva

cevc = ceuc = (quick lime)

ceuc [koik] is the Bavarian pronunciation for "Kalk" written phonetically.

Since the diphthongs *oi* and *eu* were pronounced alike the author's spelling simply reflects how he heard the word. L-vocalization means that the consonant *l* is no longer pronounced as a consonant but turns into a vowel-like sound. The spelling reflects the spoken form of the word, which in turn provides clues about the linguistic environment.

ar or (ar) t(ri)t i c us encoded words

The following words indicate that the author was familiar with a different script. At that time, it was not unusual for well-educated individuals to command more than one writing system. The script used here resembles the cipher script found in the main part of the book, which is known today as "Voynichese." The decoding is as follows:

ar _ or _ t(ri)t i c us

ar (d) or (ar) t(ri)t i c us

Ardor is a historical medical term meaning *heat*, referring specifically to inflammation. *Ardor arthriticus* was used in early medical Latin to describe the burning pain associated with gout or arthritis. The spelling suggests that the writer was familiar with Latin abbreviation practices.

The Tironian note *9* for the word ending *-us* and the suspension mark *3* for *ri* :

These are both listed in Capelli's *Lexicon Abbreviaturarum* and demonstrate that the scribe was familiar with Latin medical texts and capable of adopting contemporary abbreviation practices. The *h* in *arthr-* was not pronounced. It was omitted by the scribe because he followed the spoken form when encoding it.

It is striking that the glyph *c* is assigned multiple values - *i*, *t*, *c* [k], and *z* [ts]. This is how the glyph *2* for *t(ri)t* was invented. Suspensions depend on both context and language, and must therefore be resolved accordingly. In this case, the form could theoretically also represent *irit*, *iric*, *tric*, or *crit*, but none of these readings would make sense.

The glyph *2* resembles the character *r* of the gothic cursive but appears in an enlarged form.

The consonant *t* has a semicircular shape, with its horizontal stroke placed at the top. The vowel *i* also appears semicircular but lacks a dot. Comparable features occur in the main part of the book, where several glyphs likewise seem to carry multiple values. This could be the reason why the encrypted words often look identical, yet acquire different meanings due to the differing sound-letter correspondences. Because glyph *c* can be assigned various values, it must be interpreted in relation to both context and language. To decode its meaning, the reader would have had to try out different combinations - perhaps even in a playful manner.

Since this script has striking similarity with the encoded part of the manuscript such an encryption technique could be taken into consideration as a possible means of solving it.

Dr. Lisa Fagin Davis of the Beinecke Library at Yale University has determined, based on her specialist expertise in paleography, that the words, probably names, in the heading on folio f17r of the main section were written by the same hand as the note on f116v. Perhaps these refer to the names of those who had been selected as illustrators (Mallieu, Alber/Albar, Lucrez/Lucretius?). Unfortunately, the script has faded.

folio 17r

Heading on top of folio 17r. Written probably by the same hand as the note on f116v.

This would imply that the scribe responsible for the recipe of folio 116v also contributed to other parts of the codex. He was active not only as an apothecary or barber-surgeon but may also have taught painting and other skills perhaps in a monastic school. This was not unusual for a universal scholar in the late Middle Ages.

Folio 116v	Standard German	English	Explanation
vals v = [f]	falls	if	Not yet gemination of consonant <i>l</i> . Character <i>v</i> represents sound [f] here.
c	[tse] Zeh	toe	For the non-native German scribe the pronunciation of letter <i>c</i> and the word <i>Zeh</i> sound the same. It is simply phonetic spelling.
nv = nu	nun	now	The graphem <i>v</i> represents vowel [u] here.
z vey, v = [w]	zu weh	too painful	<i>z</i> is an Abbreviation for <i>zu</i> . The Gothic cursive <i>z</i> was often misread as an uppercase <i>B</i> . > <i>zu weh</i> (not <i>brey!</i>).
so	so, dann	then, so	
nim	nimm	take	
gasmich	Geißenmilch	goat's milk	It has nothing to do with the Engl. word "gas".

vals/vals c:

In Standard German it is *falls* (English *if*). Here, the character *v* represents sound [f]. It is the introduction to a conditional clause that continues later: *vals ... so nim* (*if ... then take ...*). In Standard German this corresponds to *falls ... so nimm ...*

In the past, this word was sometimes interpreted as the Standard German word *falsch* in connection with *falsche arzney* (meaning *wrong medicine*). The error lies in the fact that the *c* was mistakenly read as a following *e*, while the *s* was misread as *sch*. The missing spacing was not noticed.

Regarding the glyph *c* and the sequence *vals c*:

Both the letter *c* and the word *Zeh* are pronounced identically in German. This is comparable to English, where words such as *sea* or *see* can be represented by the single letter *c*, or *tea* by *t*. Shortening the full word *Zeh* to the single character *c* is very rare but historically plausible. Comparable phonetic abbreviations do occur in late-medieval and Early New High German manuscripts, especially in practical texts such as medical recipes, household books, and marginal glosses. However, the specific form found here, together with the inconsistent word separation and orthographic irregularities, suggests that the scribe was not fully confident in German orthography. The phenomenon is therefore both time-appropriate and at the same time characteristic of this particular writer.

Even though the author also uses the sign *c* for the letter *e*, such reading makes no sense in this context.

The missing separation between the words went unnoticed. It reads correctly *vals c nu* and not *valsen u*.

vey:

In Standard German it is *weh* (*painful*). The missing length marking with *h* in forms like *vey* (for *weh*) is not an error but a completely normal feature of Early New High German orthography because the use of *h* to mark vowel length developed only gradually. Therefore, the correct reading is *vals c nu z vey* and not *valsen u Brey*, as is often suggested, and it means: *if toe still too painful*. Here, too, incorrect word separation is evident. The character *v* must be interpreted as the sound *w*.

nim: (Standard German *nimm*, English *take*)

Without double consonant *m* it shows a typical medieval Early New High German and is an example of a spelling system that had not yet been standardized. Today, the German spelling is *nimm*.

gas: Standard German *Geiß*, (English *goat*)

The change *ei > a* is an exclusively Bavarian sound shift and occurs only in the Central and Southern Bavarian areas (Tyrol, Salzburg, Carinthia, southern Upper Austria, southern Lower Bavaria). The spelling in the text clearly reflects the spoken pronunciation of the scribe's immediate linguistic environment. However, in connection with the second word element *mich* for *Milch* (*milk*) it must be noted that this form does not fit a Southern Bavarian pronunciation. Southern Bavarian does not show L-vocalization but retains the consonantal *l* in *Milch*. For this reason, the word is more likely to be assigned to Central Bavarian. This, of course, presupposes that the author perceived it accurately.

The letter *s* in *gas* represents the long *s* of Gothic cursive script; it is not an *f*, since an *f* would clearly display a horizontal stroke. Nowhere in the text does a consonantal *f* appear.

mich: (Standard German *Milch*)

This word means *milk*. In parts of Austria, mainly in the East Central Bavarian dialect regions (Vienna and Lower Austria), the consonant *l* in *Milch* is weakened or vocalized, resulting in a pronunciation close to *Mich* [IPA: *miç*]. The spelling reflects this regional pronunciation. It is possible that the spoken form was *Müch*. However, in historical spelling, the vowel *i* and *ü* were often not distinguished. Medieval and early modern scribes frequently used *i* to represent both *i* and *ü*.

Now the final conditional clause reveals an unquestionably coherent meaning. It reads:

Vals c nu z' vey so nim gasmich - that is: *if toe still hurts, then take goat's milk*. The assistant is instructed that, if pain is still present, a different remedy should be prepared using goat's milk.

The language “michitonese”

The language was labeled “michitonese” because earlier reading attempts failed to recognize any linguistic structure and mistakenly read the word as *michiton* instead of *anchiton* (with spaces: *an c hi ton*). The consonant *c* [tse] stands for *Zeh* (toe) showing the author’s peculiar spelling. Both are pronounced the same.

vals c nu z vey so nim gasmich o...
 falls **Zeh** nu z' weh so nimm Geißenmilch o...
 if **toe** now too painful then take goatsmilk o...

The Illustration in the left margin

Along the left margin, besides a stomach and an goat, the multi-chambered stomach of a goat is depicted. Inside the drawing of the stomach, the German word “*lab*” is written, meaning *rennet* - the enzyme traditionally extracted from the stomachs of ruminants. Rennet is well known in the context of cheese production, where it enables the coagulation of milk. Its presence in the illustration may therefore serve as an implicit instruction regarding the intended method of obtaining this substance. The use of goat's milk as an optional ingredient is suggested, because the final sentence is: “*if toe now too painful then take goats milk...*”

Conclusion

This study suggests that the text on folio 116v of the Voynich Manuscript - which for decades was the subject of discussion and speculation - has now turned out to be a pharmaceutical note containing a coherent and comprehensible text.

Earlier interpretations that classified it as a prayer, a magical charm, meaningless “gibberish,” or merely pen-testing scribbles were largely based on faulty readings of the Gothic cursive script, on the failure to recognize dialectal phonetic spellings, and on the incorrect or missing word boundaries. By identifying the underlying language as Early New High German with Central Bavarian features, resolving the pharmaceutical abbreviations, and correctly reading previously unrecognized words, the text could be placed in its proper semantic context.

In terms of content, the note is an ointment recipe for joint pain. It is not a prescription, because no quantities are given. Its wording indicates that it was to be prepared by an assistant, as shown by the precise instructions for preparation and application.

Despite his spelling insecurity the author seems to have possessed a solid level of education and considerable medical-pharmaceutical knowledge as seen by his use of Latin terminology. However, he uses highly individual, almost arbitrary abbreviations. It appears plausible that the writer held a medical role such as that of an apothecary or barber-surgeon in a monastery.

An experimental reproduction of the recipe additionally confirmed the practical plausibility of the ingredients and preparation steps.

Some striking orthographic deviations and inconsistent spellings, such as incorrect word spacing, can convincingly be interpreted as signs of linguistic uncertainty. From this, it can be inferred that the author was not a native speaker of German.

A classification of the written language showing Central Bavarian features, makes it possible to narrow down the region of origin of this text as well as the likely place of residence of the author. The Central Bavarian dialect area can be roughly located between Munich, Salzburg and Vienna, extending southward into Styria, including Graz. Therefore, this note most likely originated in this region, while the author himself may have come from a Romance-speaking area such as Italy, Eastern France, or the Franco-Provençal region. A Slavic origin, for example from what is today Slovenia (formerly Lower Styria), cannot be ruled out, since this region was linguistically mixed. Unfortunately, due to the limited amount of textual material, this cannot be established with absolute certainty.

Of particular importance is the decipherment of two encrypted words encoding the historical medical term *ardor artriticus* (Latin for *joint inflammation*). This encryption has often led to the assumption that the passage represents some kind of blessing or magical incantation. However, it has now become clear - quite unexpectedly - that these cryptic words in fact refer to the ointment recipe described in the manuscript. In transcribing the cipher, it becomes apparent that the scribe not only heavily shortened the plaintext behind the glyphs through omissions, but also abbreviated the encrypted version itself. Some glyphs of these encrypted words, for example α \circ \mathfrak{r} \mathfrak{c} \mathfrak{g} , show notable similarities to those found in the main part of the codex. Whether a direct connection exists still requires investigation.

The parchment bearing this note was most likely a remnant from a monastic pharmacy and later made its way into the scriptorium or a monastic school, where it was reused as writing material.

Paleographic characteristics, particularly the consistent use of lowercase letters, confirm a date of origin that accords broadly with the radiocarbon dating of the parchment, situating it between approximately 1404 and 1438. The absence of double vowels and double consonants in the script may likewise be regarded as an indicator of this period. This demonstrates that the text does not originate from a significantly later period, as has often been assumed. It thereby refutes the notion of a subsequently added attribution.

After many years of intensive scholarly engagement with this part of the Voynich Manuscript, we are now in the fortunate position to determine its logical content, linguistic character, and regional background with considerably greater precision. It has become evident that the supposed “lack of structure” is not inherent to the text itself but rather results from earlier interpretative approaches. Taken together, the unexpected findings provide new lines of inquiry and may guide future research on the Voynich Manuscript in a new direction.

Acknowledgements

I would like to thank the experts, particularly from the fields of German studies, dialectology, and pharmacy, as well as the many private dialect speakers in the Bavarian-Austrian region, for their helpful insights and valuable suggestions.

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